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THE INFLUENCE OF NON-FORMAL EDUCATION ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF RURAL TOURISM IN N. MACEDONIA

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ABSTRACT

Limited knowledge and insufficient education about the meaning of tourism, especially among the population in rural areas, represents a major obstacle to successful rural tourism. Often the local population does not understand the meaning of the quality of service in tourism and is not familiar with the behaviors and expectations that tourists have during their visit to rural settlements. The paper aims to bring closer non-formal education and tourism through professional help from coordinators, coaching, training, communication tools - internet, e-mail, direct face-to-face contact through meetings and seminars to the local population in rural areas. All this will help to increase the impact at rural tourism development in N. Macedonia, in places which are healthy, good and beautiful and in places which are warm and with positive energy.

KEY WORDS: rural tourism, tourism development, non-formal education, N. Macedonia

INTRODUCTION

The perceptions of tourists, visitors and the local population regarding what is valuable in nature and in its environment have evolved over time. In recent decades these perceptions have gained greater significance by providing a new additional value to the heritage of our ancestors through the promotion of traditional knowledge and skills and through the organization of an attractive, original and rural tourist offerings. The natural beauties and resources available to N. Macedonia present great potential for the development of rural tourism, which emerged not merely as a necessity, but as a result of a rich array of authentic, cultural, natural and traditional resources and products. (<https://agrotim.mk>) Although at first glance, rural tourism may seem simple to "create", "operate" and "maintain", in reality, it requires great effort and intensive work, complemented by personal commitment, sacrifice and continuous education, both - formal or non-formal education.

One of the key roles of non-formal education is to engage all household members in creating, producing and selling traditional products, through authentic and traditional knowledge and skills. This type of initiative provides the local residents with the opportunity to earn a better income, hoping that it may reduce the emigration of the young population from the rural areas. Non-formal education aims to sustain the development of rural areas by providing professional assistance through trainings, trainings and seminars to the local population in the rural areas helping them to preserve the tradition, history, cultural values and the confections with nature. Additionally, the non-formal education helps in the preservation of local identity, in the preservation of customs, in the protection of the environment, in the strengthening of autochthonous, traditional and ecological production, (Rechkoska, 2012) that is, it helps in the development of rural environments that are visited by active, adventure-seeking tourists and visitors.

RURAL TOURISM IN N. MACEDONIA - CURRENT SITUATION

The return of tourists and visitors to the natural environments, traditional values and the activities in rural areas is a common feature of rural tourism, eco-tourism, wine and gastronomic tourism, hunting and fishing tourism, farm and agricultural tourism, cultural tourism and religious tourism. In essence, all these types of tourism can be seen not only as individual forms, but as inseparable links of the chain called **rural tourism**. Rural tourism represents

a new type of tourism with dual benefits for tourism as a whole and for the rural area.

Graph 1 Forms of rural tourism

Source: National strategy for rural tourism 2012 - 2017, 2012

Although there is no single definition of rural tourism and the concept varies across different countries, the **term** generally encompasses all the services and activities that the rural area offers to tourists and visitors, as well as to the local population.

Although there is no single definition of rural tourism and the concept varies across different countries, the term generally encompasses all the services and activities that the rural area offers to tourists and visitors, as well as to the local population. Common key elements and advantages that complement rural tourism, clarify the concept and help tourists and visitors return to traditional values are the following: (Jaszczak et al, 2010 and <http://www.bregalnica-ncp.mk>)

- the rural area and preserved nature offer an opportunity to reconnect with unique natural beauty and rarity (return to Mother Nature)
- the chance to escape the daily routine and stressful pace of urban life through a vacation or a short stay
- accommodation in traditional households, proximity to traditional gardens and courtyards, and the unique approach to preparing traditional products

-
- bed and breakfast options where tourists and visitors will have the opportunity to independently prepare food using fresh and ecologically clean products
 - the opportunity to acquire skills to prepare traditional rural food, contributing to the development of rural gastronomy
 - facing the challenges of encountering untamed nature, which raises awareness about natural resources
 - getting to know the culture, history, tradition and customs of the local population through closer contacts, communication and exchange of opinions and experiences
 - familiarizing oneself with, or participating in agricultural activities, in the tradition and way of living of the local population

From the analyzes made in the field, we can conclude that rural tourism in N. Macedonia is a relatively young tourist sector, currently in a phase that is slightly above the initial phase. This phase is characterized by an expected increase in the number of tourists and visitors, the expansion of rural tourism products, and the emergence of new businesses that will engage in constant cooperation. However, despite the positive developments and despite the excellent geographical and demographic structure that offers significant potential for rural tourism development wide across the territory, there are still obstacles preventing rural tourism from becoming one of the strategic pillars for the tourism development.

Over the past thirty years, the **Law on Tourist Activity**, (Law on Tourist Activity, Official Gazette of the RM No. 62/2004), despite the numerous amendments, it has not fully facilitated the development of rural tourism and the tourism in general. According to **Article 51** of the Law, tourist services in rural and ethnic tourism include activities such as horse rentals for riding, photo safaris, production and sale of handicrafts, souvenirs, instruments and other products and services within the rural household. These services also encompass the rental of transportation means for exploring natural beauties and services that do not harm nature in a manner determined by the specific environmental laws and by-laws. However, a significant ambiguity and inconsistency arise in paragraph 2 of the same article, where it is stipulated that tourist services can be provided by a natural person who is registered with the mayor of the municipality, and in the city of Skopje with the mayor of the corresponding municipal area. Additionally, the law requires individuals to have an agreement to act as intermediaries for those engaged in tourism, that is, catering activities, which contradicts with the concept of fostering small businesses and the entrepreneurial spirit.

In addition, as the main challenges facing the development of rural tourism in N. Macedonia the following can be singled out: (National strategy for rural tourism 2012 - 2017, 2012)

- the incomplete legal regulation in the area of rural tourism also leads to a lack of an official definition for the term rural tourism, which is more than necessary, according to WTO standards
- insufficient involvement of the central and local government, lack of cooperation and uncoordinated processes between the Centers for the Development of Planning Regions, (<https://brr.gov.mk>) Units of local self-government, the owners of the tourist facilities and local communities of the local population have led to a slowdown in expanding the products and services that the local population in rural areas can offer
- insufficiently developed policies and programs, especially incomplete national strategies, which can otherwise help the development of rural tourism as one of the fastest-growing microsegments of the market
- although the Rural Development Program of the Agency for Financial Support in Agriculture and Rural Development (<https://www.ipardpa.gov.mk/>) provides financial assistance and support, in practice, there are no equal conditions for the development of rural regions
- inefficient and ineffective use of incentives and measures from various programs and funds (IPARD, Rural Development Program, subsidies for the development of rural tourism from the Ministry of Economy) intended for local governments that should help solve problems with utility and road infrastructure in rural areas (Brief analysis 4 on the underutilized potential of rural tourism in the country, 2018)
- the small number of tourists and visitors who visited rural areas only during extended weekends, holidays or for celebrations
- the reduced activity of organizations from the non-governmental sector

A problem also arises in the section on setting the standards for tourist accommodation services in rural areas, which are generally regulated by the **Law on Catering Activities**, (Law on Catering Activities, Official Gazette of the RM No. 62/2004). However, there is no separate legal act that precisely defines, regulates and controls the standards and concepts related to rural tourism, especially those concerning tourist facilities. **Article 53** of the Law only defines that in rural households, services can be provided for the rental of rooms and apartments, where the owner or the holder of the right to use is a member of the rural household, up to a maximum of ten rooms.

Additionally, these households can prepare and serve hot and cold dishes, drinks and potions primarily of their own production, offer wine or brandy tasting services for a maximum of 50 people (excursionists) at a time.

The regulations currently applied in N. Macedonia defines a general categorization and minimum technical conditions for tourist facilities, but without specific categorization according to the standards of **EuroGites** (European Federation for Rural Tourism) (<https://www.ruraltour.eu/>), or according to the standards for rural tourism. (National strategy for rural tourism 2012 - 2017, 2012) For the services of natural persons in catering facilities within rural households in rural areas, after the mandatory categorization, they are issued a special label confirming that the external and internal arrangement of the catering the building is made with the use of natural materials, motifs from traditional culture, supplemented with folk instruments, costumes and household items such as dishes. According to **the Program for the development of tourism in N. Macedonia for the year 2024**, (<https://dejure.mk>) adopted on the basis of the Law on Tourism Activity, point 3 provides for subsidies for tourism purposes of rural households in rural areas. These subsidies can be used for building or adapting households, procuring of equipment and inventory, and reconstruction and arrangement of the space. Family households that meet the conditions will receive a sign with a "sunflower" on it, ensuring that the tourists and visitors will be confident that the rural household meets all the conditions for performing catering activities in the rural area.

However, N. Macedonia, as a country that has enormous geostrategic and anthropogenic values, where rural tourism should be experienced as a symbol of happiness and as an opportunity to introduce new elements into the environment, should "pay its debt" to smaller towns and villages. By enacting legal regulations that specifically govern rural tourism, the local population should be empowered to preserve the diversity of the landscape and culture, the natural heritage, clean air and the countless tributaries full of life and water.

*NON-FORMAL EDUCATION - TERM, CHARACTERISTICS AND
NECESSITY IN THE FIELD OF RURAL TOURISM IN N. MACEDONIA*

*Wisdom is not only a product of schooling but of the lifelong attempt to
acquire it. - Albert Einstein*

Education is the most powerful weapon that turns children into people, and people into individuals, provides stability, financial security, independence, self-confidence, helping each individual to be a part of the socio-economic part of the country and to make their contribution, which ultimately makes the world a better place, more beautiful, and safer place to live. Education as a gradual process that brings positive changes in an individual's life, work and behavior, can be simply defined as "the process of acquiring knowledge through learning or imparting knowledge through instruction or some other practical procedure." (<https://www.passionineducation.com>) If this process is implemented effectively through its basic forms (formal and non-formal education), it can contribute to the elimination of many differences and many injustices.

In general, **formal education** is compulsory to a certain extent. It is acquired in educational institutions (primary and secondary schools and higher education institutions), in accordance with predetermined curricula and plans, within a specific period of time during which students' achievements are constantly monitored. At the end of the process, students receive a certificate in the form of a diploma, which serves as the legal minimum for employment in a suitable position.

However, today's conditions of modern living, driven by constant changes in scientific knowledge and the direct influence of information technologies, demand alternative paths of education. This implies learning outside of educational institutions, independent research, acquiring new knowledge, skills, techniques, self-improvement, reading, education in private institutions, or through courses, short trainings, youth camps, volunteer exchange, workshops, conferences, and seminars. It can also be in the form of evening schools for adults, as further qualification or lifelong learning for the individual. (<https://recnik.medium.edu.mk>) **Non-formal education** can be defined as any form of voluntary education within a systemic educational institution, where curricula and programs are designed to meet the unique needs of learners, aiming to maximize learning and minimize formal elements that "occupy" professionally qualified teachers and lecturers in formal educational institutions.

(<https://www.stat.gov.mk/MetodoloskiObjasSoop.aspx?id=128&rbrObl=14>)

Non-formal education, while often treated as a synonym for **informal education**, is distinct, and is characterized by self-initiated educational activities of individuals who learn and directly acquire various life experiences. This includes learning the mother tongue, acquiring knowledge at home through electronic media and the Internet, browsing information, registering for online training, and gaining insights from social interactions. It is casual, natural, conscious, easy and informal process that occur at any time and in any place. (<https://infed.org>)

Non-formal education related to rural tourism, like in all other activities, should focus on enhancing the communication and interaction skills with tourists and visitors, as the abilities are not fully developed through formal education alone. Upskilling is essential, especially to adapt to the ever-changing habits and needs of tourists and visitors. Successful training programs for local people must be carefully selected, practical and designed to teach work skills in the simplest and most effective way. A crucial element is the selection of an individual who will conduct the training program. This person must pay close attention to their responsibilities, demonstrate technical skills and communication abilities, possess a positive attitude, and fully understand the needs of the trainees by applying high standards that justify the incurred expenses, vital for the development of rural tourism. Training is both an art and science aimed at finding, retaining and developing the knowledge and skills needed to perform the activities, duties and tasks in the field of rural tourism through the use of communication, such as: (Georgioska, 2020, Stojanovski et al, 2019 and Coverdell, 2011)

- **continuous training** - the local population must undergo constant training and retraining, including basic training through counseling, retraining and renewal of knowledge certificates
- **classroom or on-the-job training** - can be organized within or outside a work environment, such as courses, schools, academies or universities. It includes the use of video and role-playing, interactive videos, and simulations as complements to traditional written materials, lectures and discussions, mostly through simulations which help solve complicated situations
- **e- training** (electronic learning - e-learning) - with the help of the Internet, e-mail and other methods of electronic learning, it is possible to provide quality training that is both efficient and effective, thereby reducing the costs of the training itself

→ **ethical training** - aims at mastering the theory of ethics and its practical implementation through exercises that include various ethical dilemmas or problems that the local population faces in the work process and in various work activities

If the training focuses on teaching the local population how to become an effective in executing current activities and meeting the needs of tourists and visitors, then it should involve a process of developing the qualities of the local population. Skill development training is a learning process that involves the acquisition of rules or attitudes necessary for successful job completion, closely related to the complexity of the workplace. Direct mentoring and direct face-to-face contact through meetings and seminars between the mentor and the local population in rural areas should be characterized by pleasantness, smiles, relaxation, positive moral values and effective listening which is important aspect in the communication process. This approach will help solve the problems faced by the local population without displaying an authoritative force.

Picture 1: Pros and cons of non-formal education,
Source: <https://mytutorsource.com>

To better understand non-formal education, it is useful to analyze its strengths and weaknesses, which will help in recognizing the necessity of this type of education in the field of rural tourism. As advantages of non-formal learning, we can single out: (Maslak M, 2022)

- promotion of self-learning in the field of rural tourism: Since it is unplanned, and lacks structured of the programs or a definitive curriculum, everything is acquired in a natural and immediate way
- since there are no strict rules and regulations one can choose any source of acquiring education related to rural tourism
- a more accessible and democratic way of education that offers unlimited knowledge through the use of Internet tools making it more accessible.
- does not require high professional skills in the field of rural tourism, so individuals are not exposed to stress
- stimulating the interests of individuals to learn more, explore and practice their acquired meaning for the development of rural tourism
- individuals have the opportunity to valorize their knowledge, i.e., to monetize it by providing information related to the development of rural tourism

However, despite its advantages, non-formal learning also has its negative sides, which require special attention: (Maslak M, 2022)

- lack of self-confidence of individuals to be on par with well-disciplined and formally educated individuals in the field of rural tourism
- lack of encouraging atmosphere to help others to improve their knowledge, communication skills with tourists and visitors, and overall social interaction
- the flexible schedule negatively contributes as individuals may be postponing their commitments to non-formal education
- lower motivation to learn and "stick" to the lessons, because they are learned through experiences or practices without proper guidance which can result in unforeseen outcomes, and the absence of instructors leads to the inability to correct mistakes
- Internet search engines are rife with misinformation, which can lead individuals to acquire incorrect knowledge, potentially causing problems and hindering the desired development of activities related to rural tourism

Table 1 Activities in non-formal education and training by type, field, and number of courses/training activities²⁰

	2016	2022
Services		
Field of the first non-formal education activity		
Total	16 865	37 428
Courses	4 839	6 173
Workshops	7 018	5 071
Guided on-the-job training	6 103	28 920
Private lessons	:	2 150
Field of the second non-formal education activity		
Total	5 248	6 928
Courses	1 514	2 292
Workshops	3 924	2 382
Guided on-the-job training	1 976	6 419
Private lessons	-	796

Source:

https://makstat.stat.gov.mk/PXWeb/pxweb/mk/MakStat/MakStat_PazarNaTrud

Unfortunately, the situation regarding non-formal education in N. Macedonia education is worrisome. The process is overly formalized, with procedures that are too complex, consuming significant time and energy from everyone who wants to contribute because it is too formalized, the procedures are too complex and take a lot of time and energy from everyone who wants to contribute to this form of education.

²⁰ (for 2016, the data refer to persons aged 25-64, and for 2022, to persons aged 18-69)

Graph 2 Activities in non-formal education and training by type, field, and number of courses/training activities

Source:

https://makstat.stat.gov.mk/PXWeb/pxweb/mk/MakStat/MakStat_PazarNaTrud

Legal frameworks, by-laws and procedures represent a substantial limiting factor for organizations offering non-formal education. They create additional stress and fail to meet the needs of the business sector, particularly in tourism, which faces insufficient openness from formal institutions. (<https://statija.mk>) This concerning situation is also reflected in Table 1 and Graph 2, which illustrate the participation of non-formal education in the service sector, including tourism services, in N. Macedonia.

The table is divided into two categories of non-formal education activities. The first category includes only courses as the primary activities, while the second category covers workshops, seminars and workplaces training in addition to courses. These figures provide a clearer picture of the situation (<https://makstat.stat.gov.mk>). Notably, from 2016 to 2022 there was a 54.94% increase in the total number of activities (courses, workshops, seminars, and workplace trainings) However, a 27.74% decrease was observed in workshops and seminars, while workplace trainings have a significant increase of 78.89% in 2022, accounting 77.27% of the total activities in the first activity for non-formal learning. Additionally, private lessons emerged as part of educational activities in non-formal education in 2022, indicating a growing awareness among individuals of the importance of informally supplementing their knowledge, skills and competences. A similar trend is observed in the second

category of non-formal education. However, there are positive signals, and certain steps should be taken to alleviate the burden of legal and procedural hurdles. This could be achieved through the initial adaptation of best practices from developed economies, collaboration with appropriate educational institutions and experts, and by undertaking activities that facilitate the validation and sector verification of programs from acquiring knowledge, skills, and competences as well as the institutions that provide these programs. One can easily follow the Swiss model of informal education (Rogers, 2015 and hr.mk/4638-2/) which serves as an example of flexible and productive education and it can be readily adapted to our national context. This model, as a process of non-formal education involves the recognition of the knowledge, skills and competences that the individuals have acquired during life experiences, regardless of the conditions under which they were acquired. This recognition allows individuals to utilize the experience, knowledge and skills for work processes, and it is validated by a legal body. It is important to note that non-formal education is increasingly gaining recognition because it focuses on practical skills and knowledge. It has a much lower level of structure, but offers much greater flexibility that leads to the desired results - acquiring knowledge and skills that are directly applicable in rural areas. This approach provides personal development and professional growth to individuals who are ready to learn, and thus benefiting the social community by producing skilled professionals.

NON-FORMAL EDUCATION, LOCAL POPULATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF RURAL TOURISM – RECOMMENDATIONS

N. Macedonia has too many secluded and beautiful hidden places, but solitude appeals only to small a number of individuals. At the core of the Macedonian people is the belief that tourists or visitors who comes to visit should be welcomed as members of the closest family. In fact, this is the essence of rural tourism: for everyone to feel like an inseparable part of the community, to receive special attention, to be respected by all, and to be welcomed in the spirit of tradition and customs. Since a holiday in the countryside is considered an active holiday, and a visit to a village home is a themed holiday, tourists and visitors expect their needs to be met and their interests to be aligned with the lifestyle of the local population. They expect to learn about history, events, myths, legends, folklore, dialects, as well as to take care of the animals and plants that are part of the rural area. (Metodijeski, 2018) For rural tourism to succeed and gain its true meaning as a distinct tourism branch, the local population should understand the specificity of rural tourism and strive to

satisfy the wishes and needs of both tourists and visitors. This can often be achieved through the preservation of water and green areas, maintenance of footpaths, preservation of all cultural, historical and architectural sites and monuments, as well as through the production of delicious and ecologically clean products. The development of rural tourism can be represented in the simplest way through the formula CHAR: (Statev, 2007)

- C - cleanliness - purity (of nature, food, surroundings and soul)
- H - hospitality
- A - attraction
- R - rural,

if actively applied in non-formal education can yield positive results, especially due to the specific requirements of tourists and visitors who want to see and experience the authenticity of the rural area. However, to achieve positive results, the local population must be actively involved in all aspects related to the stay of tourists and visitors, and if necessary, to include individuals outside the family who will help improve the quality of services and create a positive atmosphere.

Limited knowledge and education about tourism among the local population in rural areas is a significant obstacle for successful tourism in some locations. Often the local population does not understand the importance of service quality in tourism and is unfamiliar with the behavior and expectations of tourists. Among the local population living in rural areas, it is still common to encounter unprofessional attitudes, bad habits and tastes, inadequate environmental education, inappropriate pricing for services packaging, which are issues primarily the result of the lack of experience and necessary training. Educating the local population, through training and counseling, as a special type of their empowerment. This is a planned and continuous process aiming at modifying attitudes, knowledge, skills, and behavior through experimental learning, with the aim of achieving effective performance in rural tourism. The local population should be able to offer sincere and genuine hospitality, rooted in the depths of the human psyche. Informal education, acquired through upbringing in the family, trainings, courses, classes, trainings, seminars and workshops, also represents an investment in the local population preparing them better for work and development of their rural households. This all helps them refine their skills and making the best use of their natural abilities.

All of this implies that the local population should learn to actively participate in tourism activities. They should be able to welcome tourists and visitors in tourist agencies, provide adequate answers to questions about the rural area, and to motivate them to reduce the lifestyles during their stays and anticipate new needs that will bring satisfaction, comfort, security and a sense of being respected and valued. The local population must possess certain inclinations, professionalism in staff, foster greater trust and reliability, enabling better human relations. This is particularly important in rural areas, where understanding different emotions, attitudes, and their influence on behavior can greatly aid in forming appropriate responses in various situations.

Additionally, the local population needs to learn and adopt Internet promotional tools, especially for promoting their capacities and traditional products. Organizing one-day tourist walks and experiences, offering tastings traditional specialties, and paying attention to visitor feedback can lead to valuable lesson and improvement in service quality. Establishing cooperation between the national and local tour operators, with the central and local authorities and regional development centers, will enable timely access to information about institutional support and the opportunities for the rural tourism development. Kindly greeting tourists and visitors, expressing gratitude and using positive language will enhance the impact of non-formal education on the rural tourism development in N. Macedonia. Creating environments that are healthy, welcoming and full of positive energy requires working with conscientious individuals who are professionally trained, able to handle situation with compassion, and possess professional preparation, good physical and mental health, general and aesthetic culture, personal character and moral integrity.

CONCLUSION

The development of rural tourism integrally involves introducing of new elements into the environment. However, it is essential to continuously improve the relationships between tourism, the local population, tourists, visitors and the environment. This implies proper treatment of ecosystems so that it will create as many vacation spots as possible with minimal carbon emissions, i.e., places where the local population will be encouraged to believe in a better future, gain new knowledge and skills, and to improve the living conditions in the rural areas where they reside and work. N. Macedonia is a country with a significant potential for rural tourism development, yet unfortunately this potential remains largely untapped. Domestic tour operators

“sell” rural areas as destinations only about 3-4% of the time, primarily to the international tourists and visitors seeking clean air and unspoiled nature. The local population living in those rural areas should be actively involved in this process, utilizing the Internet and e-mail, to voice their reactions when the legal frameworks, by-laws and regulations are being adopted. These regulations should not remain merely on paper but should be implemented in practice, as the local population has the best understanding of the Macedonian rural areas.

Furthermore, it is necessary to amend and simplify the legislation governing rural tourism as a sector. This could involve drafting new laws that distinguish rural tourism from the other types of tourism due to its unique characteristics and conditions. Creating adequate institutional protection and formulating a new, long-term strategy for rural tourism growth could be a viable solution. This strategy should emphasize the importance of non-formal education in rural tourism development, facilitate easier access to financing, and enhance the subsidy system which has remained unchanged for over fifteen years.

However, there is no single right or wrong form of non-formal education, especially in the context of rural tourism development. The focus should be on choosing high-quality non-formal education that would enable the local population to stand out, believe in themselves and their abilities, create comfortable experiences for tourists and visitors, actively participate in the development of rural areas, and take meaningful steps toward contributing to the development of the social and local economy. This approach will also help in the reduction of the impact of the climate change, which, at its current intensity threatens to destroy even the remaining rural areas.

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